

DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGEMENT THEORY AND PRACTICE

Xayitov Marvarbek Sherbekovich

Bukhara engineering technology institute.

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Abstract. Emergence and development of management Foreign management was created in the era of monopoly capitalism. Before its formation, there was a growing need for the separation of management tasks, the spread of management work specific to it, and the creation of its special theoretical basis. The founders of management theory are Taylor, Ford, Gilbert, Emerson, Fayol and others. Historically, the first direction of management theory was called the traditional classical school. American engineer and researcher Frederic Taylor contributed greatly to the establishment of this school. Taylor worked at all levels of the service ladder, from junior clerk to manager of a large metallurgical enterprise in Boston, USA. He applied a scientific approach to the organization of some production processes and the management of the entire enterprise in the first decision. His famous works such as "Fundamentals of Scientific Enterprise Management", "Principles and Methods of Scientific Organization of Management", "Administrative-Technical Organization of Industrial Enterprises", published abroad, laid the foundation for a large collection of literature on the scientific organization of production management. . Taylor justified the need for special functional management of labor processes, tried to separate the organization of production into structural elements along with physical labor. It is reflected in them that it is impossible to work in an old-fashioned way, that everything is thought out in advance, that all conditions and methods of work must be clear and defined in advance.

Key words: theory, practice, school of scientific management, classic in management schools, school of human relations, scientific school of property, reform, management, administrative school, convention

РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕОРИИ И ПРАКТИКИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. Возникновение и развитие менеджмента Иностраный менеджмент был создан в эпоху монополистического капитализма. До его образования возростала потребность в разделении задач управления, распространении специфической для него управленческой работы и создании ее специальной теоретической основы. Основателями теории управления являются Тейлор, Форд, Гилберт, Эмерсон, Файоль и другие. Исторически первое направление теории управления называлось традиционной классической школой. Американский инженер и исследователь Фредерик Тейлор внес большой вклад в создание этой школы. Тейлор работал на всех уровнях служебной лестницы: от младшего клерка до менеджера крупного металлургического предприятия в Бостоне, США. В первом решении он применил научный подход к организации некоторых производственных процессов и управлению всем предприятием. Его известные работы, такие как «Основы управления научным предприятием», «Принципы и методы научной организации управления», «Административно-техническая организация промышленных предприятий», изданные за рубежом, положили начало большому собранию литературы по организации научной деятельности. управления производством. Тейлор обосновывал необходимость специального функционального управления трудовыми процессами, пытался разделить организацию производства на структурные элементы наряду с

физическим трудом. В них отражено, что нельзя работать по старинке, что все заранее продумано, что все условия и методы работы должны быть ясны и определены заранее.

***Ключевые слова:** теория, практика, школа научного управления, классика в школах управления, школа человеческих отношений, научная школа собственности, реформа, менеджмент, административная школа, конвенция.*

Taylor paid a lot of attention to his intelligence. For example, he stated that the master of the room should have the following nine qualities:

1. Intelligence;
2. Specific information;
3. Work experience;
4. Etiquette;
5. Special;
6. Intelligence;
7. Honesty;
8. Thinking correctly;
9. Good health.

At the same time, Taylor said that it is very difficult to find someone who fully possesses all these qualities. Most people have only three qualities - they can be hired for a regular salary. A person with four of these qualities should be hired for a relatively high-paying job. It is very difficult to find a person who has five qualities, it is impossible to find a person who has six, seven or eight qualities. If a person with the nine qualities listed above is found, he should be accepted for the position of manager, not foreman. Taylor especially the organization of workplaces. He attached special importance to the selection of optimal methods of work, the definition of specific tasks, the correct selection and employment of people.

He made a number of recommendations on production management. For example, he distinguished 8 tasks of management activity:

1. Procedure for performance and distribution of work;
2. Compilation of drawings and manuals;
3. Time management and justification for work;
4. Compliance with discipline;
5. Determining work styles;
6. Compliance with the equipment's working order;
7. Equipment repair and maintenance

Quality control Although Taylor's functional management system is not currently used in industry, it also uses the idea of functional division of the management process in an orderly (directional) system of management.

Taylor emphasized the importance of taking into account the social aspects of administration and supply, saying that this is one of the important principles of organizing and managing production. He did not deny the methods of social demagoguery, but recommended their use. He relied on the need to ensure "class solidarity" between workers and entrepreneurs, to prevent debate between them, and considered it one of the most important tasks of management. According to Taylor, such a task can be solved only by a scientifically organized management system - management theory. Taylorism started the scientific management movement. This

movement covered the USA and spread to other capitalist countries. Taylor's system served as a basis for the development of scientific management. Garrington Emerson (1853-1931) was another major theorist in the field of economic management. He wrote the work "Twelve Principles of Productivity", and in this work he was the first to describe the system of views on the optimization of human activity.

Emerson has developed a method for achieving maximum labor productivity based on the following principles.

1. Clearly defined ideas and goals;
2. Sanity;
3. Reasonable advice;
4. Strict discipline;
5. Fair treatment of employees;
6. Centralization;
7. Fast, reliable, complete, accurate and permanent settlement;
8. Standard and procedure;
9. Moderation of conditions;
10. Standardization of operations;
11. WRITTEN standard manuals;
12. Incentive for productivity.

The drawing method of calculation and planning for the development of scientific management developed by Henry Gantt (1861-1919) and used standard motion to optimize work Frank Gilbert (1868-1924), who proposed methods of doing some work, made significant contributions. Also, the French engineer Henri Fayol made an important contribution to management theory optimization of management tasks - foresight, organization, ordering, agreement, equated to control. In 1916, his "General and Industrial Management", in 1924 The works "Scientific Organization of Labor" and "Positive Management" were published.

Made by Henry Ford created the organizational and technical principles of management of production enterprises. It's just not in the development of management techniques and organization, but in the growth of labor productivity It was also a new stage. Ford, like Taylor, is low cost and high productivity although he set a goal to achieve it, he tried to achieve it in another way. Taylor if he paid special attention to the organization of human labor, Ford used technology, technology, production focused on improving the output.

Thus, Taylor and his followers are the representatives of the first stage of the development of the theory of management, which covered the period that lasted until the 20th century, at the border of the 19th and 20th centuries, when the concept of management was created. From the 20s of the 20th century, a new stage of management development, based on large-scale capitalist production, began.

Theorists tried to replace Taylorism with a relatively flexible system. They paid attention to the social and spiritual aspects of management and included them in scientific management. Major scholars and statesmen who contributed to the development of Eastern economic ideas in some aspects of the theory of state and economic management - Farabi, Ibn Sina (X-X centuries), Khos Khajib (XI-XII centuries), Amir Temur. It is covered in the works of Ibn Khaldun (XIII-XIV centuries), Babur, Alisher Navoi (XIV-XV centuries).

Different foreign schools of management Foreign schools of management are divided into different groups depending on the nature of the laws and regulations that form the basis of management theory.

These include the following:

- "classic" school of management or "scientific management" school;
- school of "human relations";
- "emperial" school of management;
- "social systems" school;
- includes the "new" school of management.

Representatives of the classical school are American engineer and researcher F. Taylor, French scientist A. Fayol, English L. Urwick, German economist M. Weber, American G. Ford, G. Emerson. The classical school of management studies four important elements - division of labor, hierarchical and multi-level management, organizational structure, and possible limits of management. Thus, the "classical" school of management tried to establish the principles that can be applied to the management of various human activities.

He studied a number of principles of management organization. This school could not rise to the level of real scientific management theory. Ignoring the human factor characteristic of the "classical" school, approaching people's activities from a simplified point of view led to the emergence of a new direction in American management theory - the school of human relations. The founders of this trend are the Americans E. Mayo, F. Roethlisberger, Dj. Muni et al. Harvard University professor E. Mayo put forward the theory of "human relations".

The essence of his ideas is that mental and social factors are of leading importance in the labor process. Therefore, according to Mayo, all problems of production and management should be viewed from the perspective of human relations.

This theory is based on the idea that if certain social and spiritual needs of a person are satisfied, he can work more productively. D. McGregor, another representative of this school, has 2 different approaches to organizing management:

1) methods of coercion and stimulation;

2) creation of conditions for demonstrating initiative and independence as much as possible. The main aspect of this theory is that representatives of the school of "human relations" solve social problems not at the scale of the whole society, but at the scale of individual enterprises. The social situation of workers is not considered as a socio-economic problem that needs to be solved comprehensively, but as a group relationship of people.

"Emperic" (pragmatic) school denies the necessity of management and advocates open empiricism. He emphasizes that the purpose of management is to learn positive experience of leadership and existing mistakes. The representatives of this school say that it is necessary to give less theoretical advice and do more with the analysis of concrete situations, of course, experience is very important in learning.

But it is impossible to form management based only on practice. The most prominent representatives of the "Emperic" school are T. Draker, R. Davis, L. Newman, D. Miller and others. The main shortcoming of the above-mentioned foreign management schools is that they have not been thoroughly studied. This new direction prompted the creation of the School of Social Systems. Its most famous representatives are D. March, G. Simon, A. Etzioni and others. Based

on the conclusions of the "human relations" school, the school of "social systems" looks at the enterprise as a complex system consisting of a set of interrelated and interacting factors, and a person considers these factors as one.

A large group of sociologists conduct research in the field of industrial sociology. The "Social System" school strives to solve a wide range of problems compared to its predecessors, and to make the theory of management a whole. But the desire to create a theory of management led him to move away from the conditions of the current capitalist world, and as a result, it did not spread very widely. If the representatives of the "classical" school proposed to resolve conflicts by means of material incentives or equipment, and the "human relations" school proposed to resolve the production process by making the production process fair, then the "social systems" school suggested that conflicts exist in the organization.

Summary: Considering that it is a natural state, they argue that the main task is to mitigate conflicts and their consequences. At the beginning of the 50s, the "new" school had a great impact on the development of management theory. It is distinguished by the introduction of methods and methods of concrete sciences to management - mathematical modeling of decision-making, mathematical logic, programming, methods of mathematical modeling of economic processes. The most prominent representatives of the "new" school are R. Ackoff, L. Klein, V. Luce and others.

The formation of this school is connected with the development of cybernetics and the study of processes. Process studies are related to mathematical modeling of inventory management, resource allocation, replacement of obsolete equipment, optimal planning. Later, in the "new" school, an independent science - the theory of management decision-making was formed. A brief description of the development of foreign management indicates that the search for new methods and forms of management improvement continues continuously.

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